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IMPROVING POST-TRIAL ACCESS ARRANGEMENTS IN CLINICAL TRIALS IN SUB-SAHARAN AFRICA

MANUAL FOR TRAINEES

Developed by the Access Africa 1 Partners

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INTRODUCTION

Post-trial access (PTA) refers to the ethical imperative present that requires the sponsor, researchers, and relevant public health authority, "to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population or community in which the research is carried out". Law, policy, and practical guidance for PTA has so far been relatively vague but has recently attracted increased attention in the context of benefit sharing of scientific research results with low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Over the last 10 years, the number of clinical trials in LMICs has increased dramatically, with most of the trials being funded, sponsored, or otherwise influenced by private or public entities from high-income countries. This introduces the risk of exploiting study participants in low and middle-income countries who otherwise have limited access to healthcare. Hence, for all organizations that fund/facilitate clinical trials in Africa and the relevant public health authorities, in this case, the national ethics committees and the relevant drug regulation agencies, ensuring that post-trial access is in place is an ethical imperative.

AccessAfrica aims to contribute to the capacity of national ethics committees and the relevant drug regulatory agencies in Sub-Saharan Africa, in particular in Ethiopia and Uganda, to integrate PTA oversight in their functions. This means, among others, 1.) knowing the status quo of PTA in high-priority clinical trials within the region; 2.) providing practical guidance on how PTA can be enforced within the region; and 3.) developing and facilitating a PTA training workshop for national ethics committees, drug regulatory agencies and Institutional Review Boards to enforce the oversight of this ethical imperative.

This is a training manual that contains the training materials for workshops whose aim is to build capacity among key stakeholders. The manual is supplementary material to the workshop and will support the participants to get an in-depth understanding of the different PTA concepts. The training will be delivered through didactic powerpoint presentations, participatory approaches, discussion of case scenarios, and journal article discussions.

The training targets all stakeholders involved in discovery research such as Principal Investigators/Researchers, Funders and Sponsors, Research Ethics Committees, Drug regulatory agencies, community representatives, and pharmaceutical companies.

We hope that this manual will be a great companion to the workshop and that trainees will find it beneficial.

OBJECTIVES

The objectives of this training workshop are:

1. To raise awareness on the ethical principles underlying PTA in the SSA
2. To equip the trainees with knowledge of the guidelines, principles and regulations on PTA
3. To obtain feedback about PTA issues in SSA from participants

Intended Learning Outcomes:

By the end of the workshop, participants will be able to:

1. understand PTA and the ethical principles underlying PTA
2. identify ways to implement PTA in their organizations/institutions
3. understand/appreciate the challenges in implementing PTA

Training Workshop Agenda:

Training on PTA		
Training Agenda		
Time	Topic: Session 1	Facilitator/Moderator
9.00 – 9.40 am	Registration <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome remarks. • Introductions, group norms, and expectations • Aims and objectives of the training 	CLAIRE Ben K
9.40 – 9.50 am	Overview of EDCTP & ACCESSAFRICA	Ben K
Session 2		
9.50 – 10.15 am	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Definition of PTA • Historical perspectives on PTA • Ethical Principles underlying PTA 	Nassim K Rose Naluwuge Nalongo
10.15 – 10.20 am	Energizer 1	Claire
Session 3		
10.50 – 11.20 am	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Case studies of Trials with and without PTA • The proposed guideline 	Nassim Winnie
11.20 – 11.30 am	Group discussion on case studies with and without PTA	Ben K/ Nassim/ Rose
11.30 – 1.00 pm	Group presentation on case studies with and without PTA	Ben K/ Nassim/ Rose
Session 4		
2.00 – 2.30 pm	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Contemporary issues and PTA challenges • Responsibilities of key stake holders 	Rose Bernabe
3.00 – 3.30 pm	Review of the guideline	Ben K
3.30pm	Closing remarks	

Session One:

1.1 Welcome and Introductions, and ground rules

Welcome to the post-trial access training workshop!

Training Methodology: Participatory

1.2 Intended Learning Outcomes of Session 1:

By the end of the session, participants will be able to:

1. Introduced themselves, other participants and trainers
2. Describe the objectives of the training course
3. List the course ground rules and code of conduct of the training

1.3 Self Introductions

Every participant should introduce themselves and get to know each other and the facilitators.

1.4 Objectives of the training

Please review and be prepared to discuss the learning objectives for this training, found in the learning objectives, section of the manual. Your facilitators will lead you through a review of our training objectives.

1.5 Ground rules & code of conduct for the training

What rules do you think will ensure that the training runs smoothly and that participants' expectations are met? Please take a few minutes to note your ground rules.

1.6 Exercise

Please use the space below to write any ground rules for the training:

Example: 1) Respect for one another 2) Punctuality 3) Phones on silent

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

1.7 Expectations

What are your expectations? What do you want to do with what you learn? What do you want to create or change once you complete this training? Please take a few minutes to note your expectations.

1.8 Exercise

Please use the space below to write any expectations from the training:

Example: 1) I expect to learn the guidelines that govern post-trial access

1

2

3

4

5

6

7

8

9

10

Session Two A:

2.1 Historical Perspectives to Post Trial Access

Training Methodology: Didactic, Powerpoint Presentation and Participatory Case scenario discussions

2.1.1 Intended learning outcomes for session two

By end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Describe the historical issues that underpin post-trial access, and the road map to the current

2.1.2 Historical Perspectives to PTA

While there is limited practical experience and guidance on post-trial access (PTA) in clinical trials in LMICs, the concept of benefit-sharing is firmly established in international ethical guidelines.

The UNESCO Declaration on Bioethics and Human Rights, for example, highlights the duty of benefit-sharing pertaining to scientific and technological innovations, in particular with developing countries.

The Declaration of Helsinki requires the sharing of benefits in medical research with the vulnerable group.

The CIOMS International Ethical Guidelines requires multi-stakeholder cooperation to make the studied intervention and the knowledge gained available to the population or community.

Based on the principle of nonmaleficence (do no harm), PTA appears to be useful and necessary, as withdrawal of therapy may be harmful to those drawing sustained benefit from it. When an investigational drug/intervention is identified as beneficial in a clinical trial, the participants should be considered for PTA.

Hence, ethical guidelines are clear that PTA, in the form of concrete plans and procedures for benefit-sharing and access (may it be in the form of reasonable pricing of an approved indication in the host country, free or discounted prices for research participants, and the like), must be intrinsic to clinical trial planning.

2.1.3 Strong points in the international guidelines in support of PTA

2013 Declaration of Helsinki, general principle 22: “In clinical trials, the protocol must also describe appropriate arrangements for post-trial provisions.”

2013 Declaration of Helsinki, general principle 34 “In advance of a clinical trial, sponsors, researchers and host country governments should make provisions for post-trial access for all participants who still need an intervention identified as beneficial in the trial. This information must also be disclosed to participants during the informed consent process.”

CIOMS/WHO Guidelines, (2002) guideline 5:13 “Before requesting an individual’s consent to participate in research, the investigator must provide (the research subjects) the following information (...) whether, when and how any products or interventions proven by the research to be safe and effective will be made available to subjects after they have completed their participation in the research, and whether they will be expected to pay for them.”

CIOMS/WHO Guidelines, (2002) guideline 10 “Before undertaking research in a population or community with limited resources, the sponsor and the investigator must make every effort to ensure that: (...) any intervention or product developed, or knowledge generated, will be made reasonably available for the benefit of that population or community.”

CIOMS/WHO Guidelines, (2002) commentary to guideline 10 “If an investigational drug has been shown to be beneficial, the sponsor should continue to provide it to the subjects after the conclusion of the study, and pending its approval by a drug regulatory authority.”

Nuffield Council on Bioethics: “We therefore endorse the NBAC recommendation that researchers should endeavor before the initiation of a trial to secure post-trial access for effective interventions for participants in the trial and that the lack of such arrangements should have to be justified to a research ethics committee.”

2.1.4 Further reading:

https://www.nuffieldbioethics.org/assets/pdfs/HRRDC_Follow-up_Discussion_Paper.pdf

<https://cioms.ch/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/WEB-CIOMS-EthicalGuidelines.pdf>

<https://www.wma.net/wp-content/uploads/2016/11/DoH-Oct2013-JAMA.pdf>

Session Two B:

2.2 Ethical Principles Underlying PTA

Training Methodology: Didactic, PowerPoint Presentation and Participatory Case scenario discussions

2.2.1 Intended learning outcomes:

By end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Describe the ethical principles underlying post-trial access, and their applicability in clinical trials within LMICs
2. Look out for PTA provision in trial protocols
3. XXX
4. XXX

2.2.2 CIOMS principle 2;

‘Before instituting a plan to undertake research in a population or community in low-resource settings, the sponsor, researchers, and relevant public health authority must ensure that the research is responsive to the health needs or priorities of the communities or populations where the research will be conducted.

As part of their obligation, sponsors, and researchers must also:

- make every effort, in cooperation with government and other relevant stakeholders, to make available as soon as possible any intervention or product developed, and knowledge generated, for the population

or community in which the research is carried out, and to assist in building local research capacity. In some cases, to ensure an overall fair distribution of the benefits and burdens of the research, additional benefits such as investments in the local health infrastructure should be provided to the population or community; and

- consult with and engage communities in making plans for any intervention or product developed available, including the responsibilities of all relevant stakeholders.

2.2.3 Commentary on Guideline 2

General considerations. This Guideline pertains to settings in which resources are so limited that the population may be vulnerable to exploitation by sponsors and investigators from wealthier countries and communities.

The ethical standards applied should be no less stringent than they would be for research carried out in high-resource settings.

To ensure that people in low-resource settings receive equitable benefit from their participation in health-related research, this Guideline demands that local social value be created.

Low-resource settings should not be interpreted narrowly as low-resource countries. These settings might also exist in middle- and high- income countries. Moreover, a setting can change over time and no longer be considered low-resource.

2.2.4 Responsiveness of research to health needs or priorities.

The responsiveness requirement can be met by demonstrating that research is needed to provide new knowledge about the best means of addressing a health condition present in that community or region.

Where communities or policymakers have determined that research on particular health needs constitutes a public health priority, studies that address such needs seek to provide social value to the community or population and are therefore responsive to their health needs.

Concerns about responsiveness might hinge on the relevance to the community of the information a study is designed to produce. For example, a question about responsiveness might arise if a study of a new intervention is planned for a community in which established effective interventions for a health condition are not locally available and the new intervention has features that would make it difficult to implement in that community. In such cases, researchers and sponsors must consider whether the study could be made more relevant to local health needs. If the knowledge to be gained from the research is intended for use primarily for the benefit of populations other than those involved in the research, the responsiveness requirement is violated. In such cases, the research raises serious concerns about justice, which requires a fair distribution of the benefits and burdens of research (Equitable distribution of benefits and burdens in the selection of individuals and groups of participants in research).

Some research is intended to generate information relevant to the health needs of people in low resource settings but is not carried out in populations that are the intended beneficiaries of the research. As an exception to the general rule specified in this Guideline, such studies can be justified because the effort to generate information relevant to significant health needs of people in low resource settings represents an important demonstration of solidarity with burdened populations. For example, during the Ebola outbreak of 2014, phase one studies on investigational Ebola vaccines were carried out in low-resource communities not experiencing an Ebola outbreak.

Responsibilities and plans. When the research has important potential individual benefits to the population or community, the responsibility to make any intervention or product developed available to this population is shared among researchers, sponsors, governments, and civil society. For this reason, the negotiation among stakeholders must include representatives in the community or country, including, where appropriate, the national government, the health ministry, local health authorities, relevant scientific and ethics groups, as well as members of the communities from which persons are drawn, patent-holders if they are other than the sponsor, and

nongovernmental organizations such as health advocacy groups. The negotiation must address the health-care infrastructure required for safe and appropriate use of any intervention or product developed. When applicable, it must also consider the likelihood and conditions of authorization for distribution, and decisions regarding payments, royalties, subsidies, technology and intellectual property, as well as distribution costs, when such information is not proprietary. A plan to ensure the availability and distribution of successful products can require engaging with international organizations, donor governments and bilateral agencies, civil society organizations, and the private sector. The ability of the local health care infrastructure to be able to provide the intervention must be facilitated at the outset so that delivery is possible following the completion of the research.

2.2.5 Post-trial availability for communities and populations.

Even if research addresses a question that has social value for the community or population where it is carried out, the community or population will not benefit from successful research unless the knowledge and interventions that it produces are made available to them and products are reasonably priced.

Post-trial access plans are of particular concern for research conducted in low-resource settings where governments lack the means or infrastructure to make such products widely available. An investigational drug is unlikely to be generally available to the community or population until sometime after the conclusion of the study, as it may be in short supply, and in most cases could not be made generally available before a drug regulatory authority has approved it. However, other successful outcomes of research that do not require approval by a regulatory agency should be implemented as soon as feasible. An example is the introduction of male circumcision in countries with a high burden of HIV disease. Research demonstrated a significant preventive effect of male circumcision, following which, programmes to offer male circumcision were introduced in several countries. When the outcome is scientific knowledge rather than a commercial product, complex

planning or negotiation among relevant stakeholders may not be needed. There must be assurance, however, that the scientific knowledge gained will be distributed and available for the benefit of the population. To that end, agreement must be reached with the local community about the form such dissemination should take. One example might be a study that learns why a health condition such as neural tube defects is prevalent in a particular population. Another example could be a study that results in knowledge to educate the population about foods to eat or avoid in order to promote or maintain health. These requirements for post-trial availability to communities and populations must not be construed as precluding studies designed to evaluate novel therapeutic concepts. An example might be research designed to obtain preliminary evidence that a drug or a class of drugs is beneficial in treating a disease that occurs only in low-resource settings, when the research could not be carried out reasonably well in more developed communities. Such preliminary research may be justified ethically even if there will not be a specific product that could be made available to the population of the host country or community at the conclusion of the preliminary phase of its development. If the concept is found to be valid, subsequent phases of the research could result in a product that would be made reasonably available at its conclusion.

2.2.6 Additional benefits to the population or community.

Benefits other than those associated with study participation may accrue to the community or population, especially in resource-poor settings. Such benefits can include improving the health infrastructure, training laboratory personnel, and educating the public about the nature of research and the benefits resulting from a particular study. Whereas capacity-building should be a part of any research conducted in low-resource settings, other types of benefits will depend on the circumstances of the research and environment in which it is carried out. These additional benefits must be determined in consultation with the communities or the local population. Additional benefits may also include contributions that research or research

partnerships make to the overall scientific environment of such countries and communities.

2.2.7 Community engagement.

From the inception of research planning, it is important to ensure full participation of communities in all steps of the project, including discussions of the relevance of the research for the community, its risks and potential individual benefits, and how any successful products and possible financial gain will be distributed, for example through a benefit-sharing agreement. This consultation should be an open, collaborative process that involves a wide variety of participants, including community advisory boards, community representatives, and members of the population from which research participants will be recruited. Research ethics committees should require community members to disclose any conflicts of interests. Active community involvement helps to ensure the ethical and scientific quality and successful completion of proposed research. In addition, it helps the research team to understand and appreciate the research context, promotes smooth study functioning, contributes to the community's capacity to understand the research process, enables members to raise questions or concerns, and helps to build trust between the community and researchers.

2.2.8 Further reading:

<https://cioms.ch/wp-content/uploads/2017/01/WEB-CIOMS-EthicalGuidelines.pdf>

Session Three A

3.1 Guidelines for PTA in Sub-Saharan Africa

Access the AccessAfrica Guidelines on Post-Trial Access for International Clinical Trials in Sub-Saharan Africa: <https://zenodo.org/records/12600404>

Training methodology: PowerPoint Presentation

3.1.1 Learning Objectives:

- 1- To describe the AccessAfrica guidelines for PTA in Sub Saharan Africa
- 2- To discuss and improve the proposed guidelines to PTA in SSA

3.1.2 Intended Learning Outcomes:

- 1- Participants should be able to describe the proposed guidelines for PTA in SSA
- 2- Participants to be aware of the improved and updated draft of the proposed PTA guidelines for SSA

Session Three B

3.2 Case studies of Trials with and without PTA

Training methodology: Participant discussions of case scenarios

3.2.1 Learning Objectives:

To equip students with knowledge of real-life examples of PTA in research in SSA

3.2.2 Intended learning outcomes:

- 1- Participants will appreciate the real-life examples of PTA in SSA
- 2- Participants should be able to identify PTA issues in research proposals, publications, and reports.

Content

3.2.3 Case Scenarios

Participants will be asked to break into 3 groups and each group will discuss one case scenario. They will be asked to select the chairperson and the secretary who shall report the PTA issues in each case. They will be given 30 minutes to read through the case scenario and then 10 minutes of reporting.

3.2.4 Case study 1

Mrs. SB, a 61-year-old female presented to us in 2003 with the complaints of cough with expectoration, shortness of breath and weight loss of 3 months duration. She was nonsmoker, normotensive, had diabetes as well as cardio-vascular disease. She was investigated and found to have adenocarcinoma of lung. Staging workup revealed bone metastasis and she was offered standard platinum-based doublet therapy of gemcitabine and carboplatin. She was responding well to the treatment as was evidenced by chest computed tomography (CT) scan done after three cycles of chemotherapy. In the subsequent fourth and fifth cycle of treatment, her tolerance to chemotherapy was poor. During the fourth cycle of chemotherapy, she had developed Grade 4 neutropenia and she had to be given granulocyte colony stimulating factor (GCSF) support and subsequent cycle of chemotherapy was delayed by 1 week. Subsequently, in the fifth cycle of chemotherapy, she developed febrile neutropenia and Grade 4 thrombocytopenia despite standard dose reduction. She required hospitalization for supportive care and required blood product support, antibiotics and GCSF support. As she was tolerating the

chemotherapy poorly, she showed a desire to withdraw from it. At that point of time, we were actively recruiting patients for Iressa Survival Evaluation in Lung Cancer (ISEL) trial “a double blind, placebo controlled, parallel group, multicenter, randomized phase III survival study comparing ZD 1839 (Iressa, 250 mg tablet) plus best supportive care versus placebo plus best supportive care in patients with advanced non-small cell lung cancer (NSCLC) who had received one or two prior chemotherapy regimens and were refractory or intolerant to their most recent regimen.” Although discussing the further treatment options, we gave her the option of participation in the ISEL trial. She agreed to participate in the trial, tolerated the treatment well and her disease stabilized on the treatment. ISEL study results were negative and Iressa failed to significantly prolong the survival in comparison to placebo in the overall population or in patients with adenocarcinoma. The placebo-controlled phase III study investigated the effect on survival of gefitinib as second-line or third-line treatment for patients with locally advanced or metastatic NSCLC. Treatment with gefitinib was not associated with significant improvement in survival. There was pronounced heterogeneity in survival outcomes between groups of patients, with some evidence of benefit among never-smokers and patients of Asian origin. Unblinding of study was done and the patient SB was found to be on Iressa arm, responding well to treatment.

3.2.5 Discussion points

1. Summarise the Case
2. What are the ethical concerns of the study?
3. What are the clinical trial team responsibilities?
4. What are the pharmaceutical responsibilities?

3.2.6 Case study 2

Study information

Title;

Development of AntiRetroviral Therapy in Africa - a randomised trial of monitoring practice and structured treatment interruptions in the management of antiretroviral therapy in adults with HIV infection in Africa

Acronym

DART

Study hypothesis

To compare, in terms of clinical HIV disease progression or death:

1. Clinical monitoring only (CMO) versus routine regular laboratory and clinical monitoring (LCM)

The hypothesis is that CMO will result in similar outcomes to LCM, and that ART administered as pulse therapy (STI) will result in similar outcomes to continuous ART, in terms of progression of clinical HIV disease or death.

Ethics approval(s): Protocol approved in Uganda, Zimbabwe and United Kingdom

Study design: Randomised controlled trial

Condition: Human Immunodeficiency Virus (HIV), Acquired Immunodeficiency Syndrome (AIDS)

Intervention: Randomisation to Clinical Monitoring Only (CMO) or Laboratory and Clinical Monitoring (LCM):

3300 patients will be randomized to CMO or LCM over a period of 1-2 years.

Randomisation will be stratified by CD4 count (0-99, 100-199) clinical site and by third drug (Tenofovir DF, Nevirapine or NORA substudy).

Primary outcome measure

1. Efficacy: Progression to a new WHO stage 4 HIV event or death
2. Safety: Any serious adverse event, which is not HIV related

Secondary outcome measures

Progression to a new or recurrent WHO stage 4 HIV event or death

2. Progression to a new WHO stage 4 HIV event or death from 6 weeks after randomisation
3. Progression to a new or recurrent WHO stage 4 HIV event or death from 6 weeks after randomisation
4. Any grade 3 or 4 adverse events
5. Number and class of anti-HIV drugs received by 3 years
6. Time to cessation of first-line regimen for failure
7. Adherence as measured by questionnaire and pill counts
8. CD4 count at 3 years (provided that it is at least 2 months after restarting ART for those in the STI group)
9. HIV RNA viral load (performed retrospectively) at 3 years (providing that it is at least 2 months after restarting ART for those in the STI group)
10. HIV resistance profiles at 3 years in those with detectable viral load (providing that it is at least 2 months after restarting ART for those in the STI group)

Participant inclusion criteria

- 1- Documentation of HIV-1 infection: antibody-positive serology by enzyme-linked immunosorbent assay (ELISA) test (confirmed by licensed second ELISA or Western Blot).
- 2- Age ≥ 18 years
Symptomatic WHO stage 2, 3 or 4 HIV disease and CD4 < 200 cells/mm³
ART naïve (except for ART use during pregnancy for the prevention of mother-to-child HIV transmission)
- 3- Agreement and documented informed consent to be randomised to CMO or LCM and to STI or continuous ART, if eligible
- 4- Life expectancy of at least 3 months

Participant type(s): Patient, **Age group:** Adult, **Lower age limit:** 18 Years

Sex: Both

Target number of participants: 3300

Participant exclusion criteria

- 1- Cannot or unlikely to attend regularly (e.g. usual residence too far from Study Centre).
- 2- Likelihood of poor compliance. Presence of acute infection (e.g. malaria, acute hepatitis, pneumococcal pneumonia, non-typhoid salmonella septicaemia, cryptococcal meningitis). Patients may be admitted after recovery of an acute infection. Patients with tuberculosis (TB) will not be enrolled while on the intensive phase of anti-tuberculosis therapy, but should be re-evaluated after the intensive phase and a decision made then about starting ART. Patients starting ART whilst on anti-tuberculosis therapy after the intensive phase will not receive NVP, nor will they be randomised into the NORA substudy.
- 3- On chemotherapy for malignancy. Laboratory abnormalities which are a contraindication for the patient to start ART (e.g. haemoglobin <8 g/dl, total white blood cell count [WBC] <0.75 x 10⁹/l, aspartate aminotransferase [AST] or alanine aminotransferase [ALT] >5 x the upper limit of normal [ULN], grade 3 renal dysfunction - creatinine >360 µmol/l and/or urea >5 x ULN).
- 4- Pregnancy or breastfeeding

Recruitment start date: 15/01/2003, **Recruitment end date:** 28/10/2004

Countries of recruitment

England, Uganda, United Kingdom, Zimbabwe

3.2.7 Discussion points

- 1- Summarise the protocol
- 2- What are the main PTA issues in this protocol?

3.2.8 Case study 3

[https://www.hptn.org/sites/default/files/inline-files/HPTN%20084%20Prot%20v4.0 %202Nov2022 %20FINAL%20%281%29-compressed.pdf](https://www.hptn.org/sites/default/files/inline-files/HPTN%20084%20Prot%20v4.0%202Nov2022%20FINAL%20%281%29-compressed.pdf)

3.2.9 Discussion points

Summarize the protocol

What are the PTA issues in this protocol?

3.2.10 Case study 4

https://www.mtnstopshiv.org/sites/default/files/attachments/MTN-003_FINAL_Version_2.0_31DEC2010.pdf

3.2.11 Discussion points

What PTA issues are highlighted in this protocol?

3.2.12 Case study 5

https://cdn.who.int/media/docs/default-source/blue-print/sudan-ebolavirus-vaccine-protocol_uganda_webversion_december-2022.pdf?sfvrsn=bc6d4d63_3&download=true

3.2.13 Discussion points

What are the PTA issues in this protocol?

What are the consequences of having no PTA in such a trial?

3.2.14 Links to materials for further reading:

- a) <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC4394585/>
- b) <https://www.tandfonline.com/doi/full/10.1080/23294515.2019.1592264>
- c) <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/01410768221133567>
- d) <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/pii/S1935861X22001693>
- e) <https://jme.bmj.com/content/48/10/712>

- f) <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/51490877> Reasons Why Post-Trial Access to Trial Drugs Should or Need not be Ensured to Research Participants A Systematic Review

Session Four:

4 Contemporary issues in PTA and challenges of PTA and PTA Responsibilities of key stakeholders in research

Training Methodology: Didactic, PowerPoint Presentation and Participatory Case scenario discussions

4.1 Intended learning outcomes for session four

By end of this session, participants will be able to:

1. Describe the contemporary issues and/or challenges of PTA
2. Identify PTA responsibilities of key stake holders in research
3. XXX

4.2 Ethical/IRB approvals

Protocol should mention PTA provision mechanisms.

Whether experimentally proven therapy should be made accessible to the control group as well as the community from which the participants were enrolled.

Availability of standard treatment Vs new treatment.

Offering PTA may attract more trial participants (undue influence to study participation).

4.3 Technology transfer

Feasibility (technical capabilities)

Benefit sharing

Intellectual property

Existing therapies Vs New ones

4.4 Duration of provision of PTA

If posttrial access is needed, for how long it has to be provided?

Feasibility to provide PTA for an unlimited period.

How easy is it to determine the duration of PTA?

Unresolved issues regarding duration of PTA may lead to the halting of a clinical trial.

4.5 Human rights

When an investigational drug/intervention is identified as beneficial in a clinical trial, the participants should be considered for PTA.

Terminally ill patients should also have the right to get the treatment to alleviate exaggerated suffering and improve their quality of life

Who is responsible for compensation in case of injuries before approvals?

4.6 Challenges of PTA (Participants to brainstorm)

PTA issues are certainly complex, as guidelines are inconsistent and unequivocal and it remains as one of the major unresolved issues in international research.

There are many unresolved issues regarding PTA with no concrete answers (who should provide posttrial access – investigator or research sponsor or government authorities?).

High costs for conducting clinical trials may limit research in LMICs.

PTA may cause undue inducement, since the expectation of follow-up care or any other benefit, especially in LMICs, may persuade people to participate in clinical research.

PTA may delay trials because of procedures and agreements to be made with governments, sponsors, researchers and others involved.

PTA may prevent trials from happening, since the financial burden of PTA provision may become a disincentive for sponsors to conduct clinical research, especially in LMICs.

PTA may be misused as a marketing tool, as in the case of Long-Term Extension studies.

4.7 PTA Responsibilities of key stake holders

Scope of responsibilities i.e. whose responsibility is PTA?

It has been suggested that all concerned parties – sponsors, investigators, communities, and the governments involved – accept PTA as a joint responsibility and decide on its provision before the trial begins. However, there is a general belief that pharmaceutical companies and sponsors are held responsible for PTA. This could serve as a major hurdle for stakeholders to conduct clinical research.

Incorporation of PTA in national legislation/policy to prevent sponsors from evading responsibility???

	Responsibility	Implementation strategy	Outcomes
African RECs (which? National? IRBs?)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review protocols for PTA - Have a guideline/SOP for PTA review of protocols 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Require protocols to have a section on PTA - Review and include PTA in the IRB guideline 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Approved protocols with PTA section included - A guideline for review of protocols for PTA
African Regulators (which regulators?)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In addition to the above, provide an oversight to PTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - supervise the implementation of PTA - monitor and enforce PTA application 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - reports on the state of PTA annually
Healthcare authorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Formulate policies and regulations on PTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Review international and locally generated evidence and guidelines 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Policies and regulations on PTA

CT Sponsor	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - to work with in the PTA guidelines - engage with investigators to include PTA in their protocols 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide funding for PTA activities - Require investigators to include PTA in their protocols - 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - available investigational products or resources necessary for PTA - Sponsor's guideline
Local PI	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include PTA in their protocols - Negotiate with sponsor for PTA inclusion - Implementing PTA as stipulated in protocol - Including PTA in the informed consent section 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Include PTA in their protocols - Negotiate with sponsor for PTA inclusion - Implementing PTA as stipulated in protocol - Including PTA in the informed consent section 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Protocol with a section on PTA - PTA for participants at a reasonable cost or free of cost - informed consent with a section on PTA
Research participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - comprehend PTA - demand PTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - familiarizing oneself with PTA through - providing feedback for investigators - request PTA implementation through participant representatives 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledgeable participants - access to PTA - participation based on informed consent
Local community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - ensure that protocols have PTA 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - conduct a community conversation/engage 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Informed on PTA

		ment with the research team - advise the research team on PTA	- Ensuring PTA implementation in the community
Local CT inspectors	-		
Foreign funders	- Similar to sponsors		
Foreign (sponsor country) regulatory agencies	- Similar to regulators		
Foreign RECs	- Similar to REC		
Foreign CT inspectors	-		

4.8 Links to materials:

Powerpoint Slides: <https://zenodo.org/records/12600348>

AccessAfrica Guidelines on Post-Trial Access:

<https://zenodo.org/records/12600404>